

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THERMOPLASTIC COMMINGLED YARN CONSOLIDATION

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SUMMARY

The aim of the present work is the development of an experimental procedure to study the consolidation of commingled thermoplastic composites. A dynamometer, equipped with parallel plates and a forced convection oven, was used to follow the reduction of composite thickness at different pressure levels, both in dynamic and in isothermal conditions.

Keywords: thermoplastic, commingled, consolidation, sintering, impregnation

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced polymer composites are considered candidate structural materials for lightweight and fuel efficient automobiles of the future. Potential applications of these materials include body side, interior and floor panels, and in general semi-structural members. Continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites, based on commodity polymers, are attracting a growing interest essentially thanks to their fast processability, high impact and delamination strength, abrasion and chemical resistance, low moisture absorption, unlimited shelf life of raw materials, and low cost. In addition, the ability of thermoplastic matrix composites to be recycled is one of the main advantages over thermosetting in automotive industry [1, 2]. Consolidation of commingled fabrics differs from the processing of other materials because of the geometry and distribution of reinforcing fibers and matrix in the unconsolidated preforms. Several investigators [3, 4] studied impregnation and consolidation mechanisms and suggested a variety of impregnation models, usually employing Darcy's law, to describe the flow of molten matrix into the tows, with the flow direction assumed to be perpendicular to the tow axis [5]. The aim of the present work is the development of an experimental procedure to monitor the evolution of composite thickness, and consequently of the void fraction, during the compression molding of thermoplastic prepregs. Compression tests were performed using a dynamometer equipped with parallel plates with different diameters. A forced convection oven was used for temperature control during processing. Tests were performed both in isothermal and dynamic temperature mode. Two different thermoplastic hybrid yarns were used, Twintex, with iPP matrix, and Comfil, with PETG matrix.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The materials used are Twintex® T PP and COMFIL ® G.

The first material is a twill fabric with commingled E-glass and isotactic polypropylene (iPP) fibres. The material tested is a balanced woven fabric with 60% by weight of glass and 40% by weight iPP.

The second material is a hybrid yarn with E-glass and amorphous PET copolymer (PETG) fibres. The material tested is a balanced woven fabric with 60% by weight of glass and 40% by weight PETG. A SEM image of the Comfil G materials is reported in Figure 1, showing that the composite is a semi-prep, where the bundles of PETG and glass are well separated.

Figure 1: SEM Image of Comfil G hybrid yarn

Methods

Viscosity of thermoplastic matrix was measured in a ARES cone and plate rheometer, varying the shear rate between 0.1 and 10 s⁻¹ at different temperatures. The iPP and PETG matrices were extracted from the composite by milling and density separation. For iPP matrix, rheological tests were performed in a temperature range between 160 and 210°C. For PETG matrix, rheological tests were performed in a temperature range between 180°C and 250°C. The ARES rheometer was also used for measurement of complex moduli of PETG extracted from the composite, by means of torsion tests. Tests were performed at different frequencies with 0.5 and 1% strain, varying the temperature between 25 and 220°C at 0.5 and 3°C/min.

A Lloyd LR5k dynamometer, equipped with a forced convection oven, was used for measuring the thickness of the composite during consolidation at high temperatures under a constant applied pressure. Commingled yarn composite was placed between parallel plates (55 mm or 250 mm diameter), holding a constant compression force

during test. Tests were performed at different pressures, varying between 0.1 and 20 bar. Four plies were stacked between plates, with fiber aligned in the same direction for each ply. Tests were performed in isothermal and dynamic mode.

The scheme of the experimental procedure for isothermal tests is reported in Figure 2. Before each test, the upper tool position corresponding to zero thickness D_0 was measured at the same pressure used during the test. After, the composite was placed between the plates and the same pressure used for zero position determination was applied. At each time, the composite thickness was obtained as the difference between the quantity D_0 and the measured upper tool displacement:

$$s(t) = D_0 - D(t) \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

Figure 2: scheme of the compression equipment

The reduction of composite thickness was considered an indication of composite consolidation. At each time during the test, the density of the composite was obtained from its thickness as:

$$\rho(t) = \frac{Mass}{Volume} = \frac{Mass}{A * s(t)} \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

Finally, after the test, the average fiber content was measured by resin burn out tests, and the theoretical density of the composite was determined, according to ASTM D2734-94, as:

$$\rho_T = \rho_M v_M + \rho_F v_F \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

Where ρ_T is the theoretical composite density, ρ_M and ρ_F are the matrix and reinforcement densities, and v_M and v_F the relative volume fractions in the composite. Finally, the void fraction of the composite was determined as:

$$v_v = 1 - \frac{\rho(t)}{\rho_r} \quad \text{eq. 4}$$

In the calculations, a density of 890 Kg/m³ was assumed for iPP, 1300 Kg/m³ for PETG, and 2540 Kg/m³ for glass fibers.

Thermomechanical analysis (TMA) was performed on the thermoplastic matrices extracted from the semipregs by means of a Perkin Elmer TMA 7 equipped with an expansion probe. Fibers were pulverized by means of a Retsch Z100 ultracentrifugal mill, equipped with a 0.5 mm sieve. Powders were placed in the TMA apparatus. During each test, holding a constant force on the sample and varying the temperature results in a decrease of the sample thickness, due to polymer sintering [6]. Accordingly, neglecting the density variation of the polymer due to thermal expansion, the thickness of the sample δ can be related to the bulk density ρ_B by:

$$\rho_B(t) = \frac{Mass}{Volume} = \frac{Mass}{A_r * \delta(t)} \quad \text{eq. 5}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental curves for Comfil G consolidation in dynamic temperature tests at different pressure levels are reported in Figure 3. As it can be observed, the composite thickness decreases with increasing temperature. At each temperature, the composite thickness decreases with increasing pressure. The derivative of the consolidation curve is reported in Figure 4. Three different steps, well separated on the temperature axis, can be observed. The first step, observed at temperatures slightly higher than matrix T_g (which is about 72°C as observed by calorimetric analysis) is due to PETG modulus decrease and plastic deformation of fibers. The second step, showing a peak at 120°C, is due to PETG fibre sintering [7]. The third step, observed in Figure 4 as the peak at 190°C, is attributed to fibre impregnation and void removal.

The TMA analysis performed on the PETG matrix, reported in Figure 5, shows that sintering of the PETG matrix takes place between 75 and 150°C. The derivative of TMA curve shows two distinct peaks. The first one is observed at about 75°C and can be related to the same phenomenon observed in consolidation experiment (first peak in Figure 4): again the plastic deformation of PETG fibers above the glass transition temperature. Correspondingly, the second peak, observed at about 120°C as in Figure 4, is attributed to PETG powder sintering.

Figure 3: consolidation of Comfil G PETG semi-preg

Figure 4: derivative of the compaction curve for COMFIL G PETG semi-preg

Figure 5: TMA sintering curve for PETG matrix

The SEM images obtained for Comfil after thermal treatment at 180°C (before the third consolidation step) is reported in Figure 6, showing the presence of a well consolidated PETG matrix. On the other hand, no evidence of glass fiber impregnation can be observed in Figure 6, indicating that the very high viscosity of the resin for temperatures lower than 180°C favours sintering rather than polymer matrix flow and fibre impregnation.

Figure 6: SEM image of Comfil after thermal treatment to 180°C

The consolidation behaviour of PETG matrix composite can be better understood by looking at the results from DMA analysis, reported in Figure 7 for PETG matrix. The PETG material shows a distinct glass transition signal about 87°C, with an onset about at 70°C, followed by a wide rubbery plateau. During consolidation tests, when the temperature exceeds the glass transition temperature of the matrix, the modulus reduction causes the plastic deformation of PETG fibers, still retaining elastic properties. At higher temperatures, and sufficiently long times, the polymer viscosity is low enough to allow viscous sintering of fibers. Nevertheless, the viscosity of the material is, at this stage, too high to allow any fiber impregnation. Above 180 °C G' is decreased of an order of magnitude making possible a viscous flow. As a consequence, fiber impregnation can take place, and the composite thickness decreases as observed in Figure 4 for the COMFIL composite.

Figure 7: complex moduli for PETG matrix as a function of temperature

In the viscous flow region of the PETG matrix, the rheological characteristic of the material were determined by cone and plate rheometry. Results reported in Figure 8 show the strongly non Newtonian behaviour of the PETG matrix.

Figure 8: rheological curves for PETG at different temperatures

The viscosity curves were fitted by a power law model, yielding the regression parameters reported in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.** As it can be observed, the viscosity at 1 s^{-1} shear rate decreases with increasing temperature, whereas the power law index n increases with temperature, indicating that the behaviour of the material changes from strongly non-Newtonian to weakly non-Newtonian.

Table I: regression parameters for PETG viscosity curves at different temperatures

Temperature [°C]	$\eta (\dot{\gamma}=1\text{s}^{-1})$ (Pa*s)	n
180	5370	0.62
200	2162	0.66
210	794	0.87
220	489	0.81
250	154	0.85

As it can be observed, the viscosity is very high at a temperature of 180°C , and significantly decreases in a temperature interval of 20°C , up to 200°C . This indicates that the onset temperature for polymer flow is about 180°C , which is in agreement with composite consolidation curves of Figure 3. The results reported in Figure 3-Figure 8 indicate that the consolidation behaviour of the COMFIL composite is a three stage process, influenced by the viscosity of the matrix and by the distribution of bundles. In particular, referring to the model developed by Bernet et al [8] the first stage of consolidation is the formation of a homogeneous polymer pool, which is governed by plastic deformation of polymer fibers and sintering. The second stage is the

impregnation step, which can be modelled through the Darcy law. In particular, concerning the sintering step, different approaches can be found for spherical-like particles, as those found in rotational moulding. In the case of composite compaction, a cylindrical geometry should be used, and the rate of sintering mainly depends on fiber diameter, and surface tension.

Experimental curves for Twintex PP consolidation at different pressure levels during a heating scan are reported in Figure 9, showing that the compaction of the composite takes place after melting of the matrix. The consolidation efficiency increases with the applied pressure. Two different steps can be observed, the first one involving fiber impregnation, and the second one void coalescence and matrix flow at the laminate boundaries [9]. In particular, the first step of the consolidation curve reported in Figure 9 can be explained by observing the TMA curve of iPP matrix. The sintering curve shows a single peak, placed at 185°C, due to fiber coalescence. The peak in TMA curve roughly coincides with the consolidation curve derivative, indicating that matrix fiber coalescence is the main mechanism involved in composite consolidation.

Figure 9: consolidation curve of Twintex PP commingled fabric

Figure 10: TMA sintering curve for iPP

Conclusions

The experimental procedure described in the present work is suitable to study the consolidation behaviour of thermoplastic matrix composite. The presented results showed that the consolidation behaviour of the composite is strongly dependent on the nature of the composite matrix as well as to the level of pre-impregnation of matrix and reinforcement fibre. In particular, it is shown that for commingled fabrics the compaction takes place due to fibre impregnation after homogenous matrix regions are formed. For amorphous matrix semi-pregs consolidation takes place in three different steps. After a plastic deformation of the rubbery matrix above T_g , polymer fibres are sintered when the viscosity of the amorphous polymer matrix is still very high. Then fibre impregnation, requiring a lower viscosity, occurs at higher temperatures. If the polymer matrix is semicrystalline, consolidation follows a simpler path taking place at a temperature immediately above melting.

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